

Wealth Acquisition Addiction: The Nigerian Quandary

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Abstract:- This paper explores the concept of Wealth Acquisition Addiction as a behavioural addiction, though not classified in the Fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual for Mental Disorders (DSM-5-TR) as a behavioural addiction, Wealth Acquisition Addiction was found to possess some phenomenological similarities in its manifestation with other behavioural addictions and with substance abuse. The paper also attempts to explain the construct of Wealth Acquisition Addiction from the Nigerian perspective, using the Machiavellian Theory of Wealth Acquisition, which can be construed as portraying that “the end justifies the means” or the “steal but do not get caught” philosophies; and the inequality in wealth distribution, as a causative factor, of the obsessive desire to acquire wealth among some Nigerians. Factors that may contribute to Wealth Acquisition Addiction, such as addictive personality, substance abuse and genetics, were explored. The paper critically discussed the psychosocial implications and signs of Wealth Acquisition Addiction, and proffered psychological approaches to the treatment of Wealth Acquisition Addiction. The need for further empirical and epidemiologic studies on Wealth Acquisition Addiction was suggested.

Keywords:- *Wealth Acquisition, Addiction, Quandary, Money.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Not all addictions are drug or alcohol related, some behaviours have over the years gained the interest of psychologists, as being addictive because they trigger the same physiological reactions in the brain, as a would an addictive substance. These behaviours have been termed Behavioural addictions or Process Addictions. Despite not being classified in the Fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual for Mental Disorders (DSM-5-TR) as a behavioural addiction, Wealth Acquisition Addiction, is a term coined to describe the maladaptive behaviours and negative attitude towards money and the acquisition of money, (such as the way an individual may act when he has money, when he is trying to acquire money or when he is without money), which resultantly affects other significant aspect of the individual's life and functioning.

Although they do not depend on substances, behavioural addictions such as Wealth Acquisition Addiction (WAA) can be extremely dangerous and harmful, as people who suffer from this experience considerable deterioration in other

significant areas of their lives. The reactions to WAA are similar to drugs or substance addictions, in their characteristics and consequences. The individual who is addicted to wealth acquisition, prioritizes his relationship with money, and relegates other relationship he has with other people to the background. The observed inequality in economic and income distribution, has led to the stark desire of many to rise above the prevalent poverty level. This has resulted in most Nigerians struggling to partake in a share of the ‘national cake’ from crude oil proceeds or political positions; irrespective of how illegal, or unethical the means maybe, so as to acquire wealth.

Wealth acquisition has been implicated to cause a sense of moral entitlement, contribute to increase in crime rates (Oluwunmi, 2010), lead to the disruption of marriages, spoil careers, restrict artistic creativity, lead to depression, and to ‘questioned’ integrity. Unrestrained desire to acquire wealth can reduce the quality of an individuals’ life. There is a strong association between some behavioural addictions (Grant, Potenza, Weinstein, & Gorelic, 2010), such as Wealth Acquisition Addiction and depressive and anxiety disorders

II. WEALTH ACQUISITION

Defining wealth can be a normative process, with varying standards and implications. Kiyosaki & Lechter, (1998) defined wealth as the accumulation of income producing assets. He did not view wealth as just money, but as systems through which money can be generated. Various definitions and concept of wealth have been asserted by various individuals and in different contexts. McGee, (2012) defined true wealth as having a “sense of abundance”, that can be experienced rather than possessed. Generally, Wealth can be referred to as a huge expanse of money or assets that an individual owns; it is also the state of being rich or having copious and substantial resources or possessions. Wealth may be measured by estimating all the valuable possessions owned by an individual, such as money, assets or properties. However, for this paper, wealth and money will be used interchangeably.

According to these authors, Akah & Uzoh, (2019), the “get rich quick” syndrome is as a result of greed, love for materialism, and a twisted social, which is infamously prevalent in the Nigerian clime. Ordinarily, it is acceptable for an individual to aspire acquiring material possessions, however when such desires become disproportionate,

uncontrollable and excessive, then it be described as maladaptive. Individuals, who place wealth acquisitions paramount above all else, generally tend to, measure their personal accomplishments and that of others on the premise of how much wealth they have amassed. Excessive desire for material wealth may be as a result of the society's distorted values and preeminence given to wealth. The society seems to recognize and acknowledge the wealthy, who may have cut corners in their bid to acquire wealth. There is a consensus among authors that the desire to acquire wealth has led some individual to crimes, such as theft, burglary, assassinations, internet fraud, forgery, prostitution, kidnapping, drug and human trafficking (Oluwunmi, 2010; Akah, & Uzoh, 2019). Adama, (2015) posits that excessive desire to amass wealth is the greatest social ill of our society, with corrupt leadership, greed and lack of security being responsible for this.

Furthermore, fear of the future has also been identified as another factor for the inordinate desire to acquire wealth. Kiyosaki & Lechter (1998) posits that individuals are controlled by two emotions- fear for the future/unknown and greed for money. Individuals who use money to alter their mood may consequently develop uncontrollable relationship with money; by being overly fixated on ways to acquire more of it, how they intend to spend it, and ways they can use it to manipulate other people (Dayton, 2011).

III. ADDICTION

Addiction refers to a state of being "highly devoted" to an activity, or behaviour, which may have resultant negative implications. Repeated engagement in addictive behaviours increases the risk of the side effects from the said behaviour. Even when there are no negative consequences, if the individual finds the behaviour/experience gratifying, the addictive behaviour is likely to continue; and may not even be considered addictive. The behaviour may become a lifestyle or a means of existence. Studies have shown that continuous engagement in an addictive behaviour reduces the likelihood of the person engaging in alternative behaviours (Sussman & Sussman, 2011).

Dayton (2011) defined process addictions as a compulsive, 'out of control' devotion to behaviours, such as gambling, sex or wealth (money). Authors have suggested that there is a similarity in the 'mood altering'/physiological changes in the brain between process addictions and substance addiction. Addictive behaviours like watching pornography and obsessive eating triggers the release neurotransmitters such as dopamine, which give a 'high' that is similar to the kind that is gotten from an addictive substance, thereby making the brain to react to such behaviours as it would to substance. (Dayton, 2011).

Addiction may occur from the interplay between psychological factors, an individual's social environment and the type of addictive behaviour (Griffiths, 2015). Addiction

may occur in various forms; however it is often presumed that physical dependence characterized by withdrawal symptoms is necessary for a diagnosis of addiction disorder to be made. For most behavioural addiction, such as wealth acquisition addiction; addictive tendencies may occur without the presentation of physical dependency issues, as is present in drug and alcohol addiction.

Studies on behavioural addictions are a seen as controversial, as they revolve between the notion of impulse control disorders and substance use disorders. This is an evolving subject, which in recent times has generated so much interest and debate among psychologists; one of such issues is the conceptualization of the construct of behavioural addiction (Starcevic, & Khazaal, 2017). The American Psychological Association's Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5-TR) classifies only gambling disorder as a behavioural addiction; However, all behavioural addictions have similar manifestation. Despite not being classified in the Fifth edition of the DSM (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual for Mental Disorders) as a behavioural addiction, wealth acquisition addiction, is a term coined to describe the maladaptive behaviours and negative attitude towards money and the acquisition of money, (such as the way an individual act when he has money, when he is trying to acquire money or when he is without money), which resultantly affects other aspects of the person's life and functioning.

Studies have shown that behavioural addictions mimic substance addictions in many ways, such as their history, experience of the abuser, 'tolerance, comorbidity, overlapping genetic contribution, neurobiological mechanisms and response to treatment' (Grant, Potenza, Weinstein, & Gorelic, 2010). Although they do not depend on substance, behavioural addictions such as wealth acquisition addiction can extremely be dangerous and detrimental to the individual and to others around him. People who suffer from WAA (wealth acquisition addiction) experience considerable deterioration in consequential area of their lives. The reaction to WAA is in some ways similar to drug or substance addictions in their characteristics and consequences.

IV. COMMON FEATURES OF BEHAVIOURAL ADDICTIONS (SUCH AS WEALTH ACQUISITION ADDICTION) AND SUBSTANCE ABUSE

One may wonder the likelihood of being addicted to a substance or object that does not enter into the body. The human brain has the ability to react to behaviours the same way it reacts to drugs or alcohol. Substance abuser experience a lack of control over the substance of their interest, they may however elicit some short-term rewards from the said substance; similarly, some behaviours also produce short-term rewards, with a resultant in of lack of control over the said behaviours. Diminished or reduced control is a significant characteristic of substance addiction, and controversially,

behaviour addictions. Evidence has indicated that certain behaviours provoke a ‘strong reinforcement’ in the human brain, that may make a person want to repeat the same behaviour repeatedly, irrespective of how disruptive it may be to the person’s life and psychosocial functioning. The reinforcement of these behaviours (positive or otherwise) may be so established that the person experiences some form of withdrawal symptoms when they try to discontinue the behaviour; just as in substance addiction. They may begin to experience agitation, insomnia, behavioural/personality changes and irritability. (Grant, Odlaug, & Chamberlain, 2016).

This means that tolerance will increase just as with mood altering substance, and the individual may need to frequently engage in more of these activities, to be able to attain the same ‘highness’ that just a little provided before. Because of this, they become increasingly preoccupied with all things related to getting and maintaining their substance (in this case, wealth) to the exclusion of other things (Dayton, 2011).

Another critical characteristic of behavioural addictions (in its phenomenological similarity with substance addictions), is the individual’s inability to control his desire or impulse to continue in the worrisome behaviours/activities; irrespective of the ill effect the repetitive engagement of the said behaviour may be exerting on other significant aspects of the person’s life (Grant, Potenza, Weinstein, & Gorelic, 2010).

There is also a trend of financial, social and relational loss in substance use disorders as well as in behavioural addictions. Persons with behavioural addictions such as wealth acquisition addiction; like those with substance addictions, in their bid to fund their maladaptive behaviours, have often been implicated in crimes such as in fraud, stealing, robbery, (Grant, Potenza, Weinstein, & Gorelic, 2010) or just for intrinsic gratification of the desire to acquire more wealth.

➤ *The Machiavellian Theory of Wealth Acquisition: The Nigerian perspective*

“Machiavellianism” refers to Niccolo Machiavelli’s socio-political viewpoint on the acquisition of power. The crux of his belief can be summarized thus “the end justifies the means”. His philosophy postulated that one can employ ‘any’ means necessary in the pursuance of his desired goals. And that the desired goal (power/wealth/influence) must be safe guided by any means possible. The central theme of the Machiavelli’s theory is the acquisition, retention and expansion of power. This acquisition of power can be garnered through war, conflicts, lobbying, by skills, or other disreputable means. There is no respect for ethics, conscience or principles, rather importance is placed on success, and not the means of the success. And this is the only standard by which all political actions are measured (Oyekunle, 2015).

The approach of wealth acquisition presently practiced by some Nigerians in recent times is the philosophy of “steal and grow rich but don’t be caught” which can be deduced as an orientation of the Machiavellian beliefs of “the end justifies the means”, This principle of “steal and grow rich but don’t be caught” have been observed to strongly propel the activities of some dishonest Nigerians. This concept is premised on the concept that it is practically far-fetched for someone to acquire wealth without getting involved in illegal and indiscriminate dealings. Thereby making some of them perceive morality and wealth acquisition as two distant opposites; as one must be given up for the other (Ochulor, & Metuonu, 2013).

➤ *Wealth Acquisition Addiction and Wealth Inequality: The Nigerian Perspective*

Nigeria is the most populated country in Africa. It covers millions of land acres, with over 38.5 billion barrels of reserved oil. It is endowed with massive gas reserves, minerals and human capital resources. Nigeria is one of the top world exporters of oil and is the second largest economy in Africa. Despite all these immense human and economic resources, it still has more than 50% of its population living in abject poverty, because of its unutilized human and economic resources (Igwe, Adebayo, Olakanmi, Ogbonna, & Aina, 2013).

There is reported inequality in Nigerian’s distribution of wealth, as it has been purported that only five of Nigerian’s richest men can remove about half of Nigerians population from poverty. There seems to be an inadequate or rather infantile plan to level the economic divide or to evenly distribute the naturally endowed resources of the country, which has further deepened the experienced inequities across generations and regions (Ekeruche, 2017).

Ogbeide and Agu (2015) defined income inequality as the ‘inequitable distribution of income among the members of a particular group, an economy or society’

The rapid increase in wealth and income inequality has been a cause of concern for economic analyst; and has been assumed to be a sustaining factor of diffidence on the economy and on the social configuration of any country (Berman, Ben-Jacob & Shapira, 2016). The increase in the level of economic inequality in Nigeria is so significant that people struggle daily to make ends meet, even when the nation is riddled with enormous wealth in the control of very few persons.

It has been opined that poverty and inequality in Nigeria are as a result of the fraudulent appropriation, mismanagement and the embezzlement of resources, rather than the lack of resources (Mayah, 2017). The perceived wealthy people and those in prominent political positions are not inclined to see the economic inequality. They seem to be blind to it and this may have far-reaching implications on how our leaders are elected or educated (Szalavitz, 2010). At the face of this stark

reality, is the desire to rise above the poverty level which is very prevalent. Nzurumike, (2019), posits that the desire for wealth by human being is normal but the rate at which Nigerians go after this is exceedingly alarming. The economic structural and situational variables in Nigeria, coupled with other predisposing factors may be implicated for this obscene desire to acquire wealth, even at grave risks to the individual and to their loved ones. Akah, & Uzoh, (2019) noted that the excessive desire for wealth acquisition is a common phenomenon, which involves a greedy and insatiable crave for material things; this social malady, seem to be widespread among many Nigerians, since our society tend to acknowledge individuals who cut-corners, in their bid to acquire wealth; thereby trivializing the virtue of hard work.

More so, government officials often assume that their position is a means to amass wealth, fame and ‘connections’. Ironically, the present philosophy of wealth acquisition for some Nigerians can be articulated as “anything goes”, “steal and grow rich but thou should not be caught”, “employ whatever means available to achieve your ends”, “the end justifies the means” Some individuals in their quest for acquiring wealth involve their selves in paranormal activities, such as cultism, charms, ritual killings (Ochulor & Metuonu, (2013).

➤ *Understanding the Concept of Wealth Acquisition Addiction*

An individual with Wealth Acquisition Addiction, (just like in substance addiction), has an obsession with money, and this obsession becomes their primary priority and relationship. The relationship this individual has with money is their most prized connection, hence, every other relationship (including relational and social) becomes secondary. Their motivation, worth and identity is enveloped in that desire to acquire money, that they do not know who they would be without the money. As time goes, these individual’s sense of identity and mood becomes excessively dependent on an external object, just like in substance addiction (Dayton, 2011). Thoughts may be preoccupied with contents such as “who would I be without my money”?

It is no accident that seeing money as a process addiction has risen out of the addictions field. The money-obsessed individual may possess an uncanny control over other members of his family; as he may wield money as a tool of manipulation. Money may also be interlaced with social relationships, where the individual begins to see family members and others based on their economic or financial worth, that is through the lens of money (how much are their worth or how much asset they have). They may find it difficult to differentiate between real affection and an affection that can be “bought” with money. This attitude may hamper on the personal growth of the individual and those around him (Dayton, 2011).

➤ *Factors That May Contribute to Behavioural Addiction-Wealth Acquisition Addiction*

Certain personality traits, substance addiction and genetics, has been purported to contribute to behavioural addiction. Addictive personality trait has been shown to be prevalent among people who suffer from substance abuse and behavioural addictions. Studies have suggested that people with a high score in personality and behaviour assessments for impulsivity and sensation-seeking, are significantly likely to engage in a process addiction. Similarly, people who score low on harm-avoidance are also more likely to suffer from a behavioural addiction (Grant, Potenza, Weinstein, & Gorelic, 2010).

Researchers have suggested that there is relationship between substance abuse and behavioural addictions; as people who misuse substance are likely to be engaged in an addictive behaviour such as gambling and money-obsession. Also, genetics has been indicated as a risk factor for the development of a behavioural addiction. An individual with a first-degree relative, who is a process addict, is more likely to suffer from a behavioural or substance addiction. A study by Grant, Potenza, Weinstein, and Gorelic, (2010) among identical and fraternal twins showed that genes play a critical role in determining the risk of gambling addiction in 12–20% of the studied population; whereas environmental factors make up about 3–8%. Further research has shown that 64% of the risk of developing both a gambling addiction and an alcohol use disorder can be attributed to genetics. More research may be necessary to ascertain if genes significantly increase the risk of other behavioural addictions such as Wealth Acquisition Addiction.

➤ *Psychosocial Implication to Wealth Acquisition Addiction*

Some studies have suggested that the more a person becomes richer, the less he ‘connects’ with other people. And that wealth suppresses empathy and compassion in some individuals (Gregoire, 2017; Monbiot, 2019). Persons from lower economic status have been shown to express empathy and have been indicated as having superior emotional intelligence, more than the financially elite (Gregoire, 2017).

Wealth acquisition has been implicated to cause a sense of moral entitlement, disrupt relationships, reduce creativity, cause depression, may reduce quality of life, alter mood and lower self-esteem. There is a strong association between some behavioural addictions, such as Wealth Acquisition Addiction with depressive and anxiety disorders (Grant, Potenza, Weinstein, & Gorelic, 2010).

Wealth addiction has a common pathway with other addictions, in that the level of addiction gets worse, and the abuser obviously loses control over the behaviour (Zwolinski, 2010).

Additionally, the acquisition of sudden wealth can lead to loneliness; as people who acquire sudden wealth often feel isolated and miserable. When an individual suddenly becomes wealthy, the effect is intense as it affects every part of the person's life. This psychosocial consequence arises mostly from difficult relationships with others; as the person may begin to doubt the intention/love of his family and friends, and may feel that the love they show him is because of his sudden wealth acquisition, this can lead to the individual alienating himself (Elizabeth, 2017).

On the flip side, individuals who perceive their selves as not wealthy, often 'judge and stereotype' the perceived wealthy as being 'cold and unsympathetic'. Some studies have suggested that wealth/ riches do not in itself lead to unhappiness, but high score in materialistic index has been linked to lower relationship satisfaction, and that perceived rich individuals may be more predisposed to depression than others (Gregoire, 2017).

Interestingly, individuals who perceive their selves as wealthy tend to be tightfisted and stingy. Indicators have shown that they do not give proportionately to the amount of their wealth, as do those in the lower economic strata. This may be because they see any substantial donation as a reduction in their worth, self-image, self-esteem and influence (Seltzer, 2011).

➤ *Signs of Wealth Acquisition Addiction*

Just as in other addictive behaviours, like food addiction and alcohol addiction these signs are also prevalent in Wealth Acquisition Addiction: denial, shame and secrecy, obsessions, lack of control, and an inability to modify the problem behaviour despite the observed negative consequences.

➤ *Denial*

One of the signs of wealth acquisition addiction is that the individual will be in denial of his exact financial status. They tend to be vague about money: their expenses, earning, and debt, how much money they have in their bank account. They live in a hazy financial fog. Denial can also take the form of not having any financial goals in place, like a retirement plan or savings plan. The individual may cope with that denial by telling himself that a magical solution will appear to make things better. It's important to realize that denial doesn't just apply to people who are compulsive spenders and chronic debtors. It can also apply to someone who is an excessive saver, and unable to face the reality that they do not have enough money in the bank to spend. The problem here is that people are putting too much emphasis on the "number" they think they need to be happy. This denial may also hold the individual back from getting help, as they may not be ready to face the idea of new actions and habits, and instead choose to stay stuck and in their ways, which could be to their detriment (McCall, 2016).

➤ *Money Secrecy & Shame*

This is the tendency for an individual who is struggling with money, to feel shame about his money problem and consequently, be secretive about it, because he may not want to be judged for not being able to manage his finances, or he may not want to be looked at as a failure. Another case may be when the individual sometimes spend in ways that are destructive, and feel like they must keep it to themselves. The secret starts to fester, making them feel shameful about not only what they did, but the fact that they are hiding it. In some cases, it can lead to acting out with more impulsive spending. Just like with any addiction, trying to hide shame and money issues makes one isolate himself from the people and resources that could actually help him. And the more isolated the person become, the worse they feel.

➤ *Money Obsession*

This refers to the inclination to constantly think about money. How it will be acquired, how it will be spent and how it will be managed. These individuals are constantly running numbers in their head. Just like in other behavioural addictions, the individual spends the majority of their time engaging in the money obsession, thinking about, arranging ways and schemes to get it, or recovering from the effects of such obsession (Hartney, 2019). This is to someone who goes on a strict diet, who gets extremely obsessive about calorie counting. This obsession begins to take a real toll when the individual cannot calm their thoughts, hence leading to insomnia. Apprehensions about money may occupy the emotional and mental space that was previously dedicated to 'enjoying life and being with loved ones' (McCall, 2016).

➤ *Lack of Money Control*

When an individual is unable to change their money habits and behaviours, the person is deemed to have little or no control over this aspect of their life. They have trouble cutting back despite wanting to stop. This lack of control may start to derail the person's self-confidence. They may begin to doubt their self, and lose trust in their inherent abilities.

➤ *Inability to Change Money Behaviour despite Negative Consequences*

Similar to lack of control is the idea that even faced with serious consequences of money behaviours, such as a dissolving marriage, bankruptcy, loss of property, maxed out credit cards, the individual may still be unable to manage his money appropriately (McCall, 2016).

➤ *Psychological Approaches to the Treatment of Wealth Acquisition Addiction*

There are no pharmacological treatment currently approved for the treatment of behavioural addictions, however, psychosocial interventions that is premised on a relapse prevention model has been shown to be beneficial. This model of intervention encourages self-restraint by identifying 'patterns of abuse', and teaches the abuser how to cope with situation; while making lifestyle changes that

reinforces healthier behaviours (Grant, Potenza, Weinstein, & Gorelic, 2010).

The first step in the treatment of Wealth Acquisition Disorder is for the individual must accept that he has a maladaptive behaviour and attitude towards money, and then make a decision to actively seek out help. Behavioural addiction is a treatable condition. Cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) is the most common form of psychotherapy used in treating behavioural addictions, such as Wealth Acquisition Addiction. It focuses on identifying patterns that trigger compulsive behaviour and making lifestyle changes to promote healthier behaviours. Currently, there are no medications approved for treatment of behavioural addictions in general. Any unrelated psychiatric disorders should be kept under control, and differentiated from the contributing factors that cause the addiction (Grant, Potenza, Weinstein, & Gorelic, 2010).

Scholars have stated that including cognitive restructuring strategies in CBT programs and motivational interviewing, in the treatment of individuals with behavioural addictions have shown evidence-based success. These psychosocial intervention strategies will help to weaken the irrational beliefs, such as the philosophies of “steal and grow rich but don’t get caught” and “the end justifies the means”, with other maladaptive thought pattern associated with this disorder (Menchon, Mestre-Bach, Steward, Fernández-Aranda, & Jiménez-Murciam, 2018).

Making significant and lasting behavioural changes is an “inside job”. It takes time, and the guidance of psychotherapist who can weave together the deeper layer of issues that may be the causative factor of the maladaptive behaviours, while also helping the individual acquire better attitude toward money and adapt better coping strategies.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATION

This study examines the concept of Wealth Acquisition Addiction, as a Nigerian quandary. Wealth Acquisition Addiction, is a term coined to describe the maladaptive behaviours and negative attitude towards money and the acquisition of money, (such as the way an individual act when he has money, when he is trying to acquire money or when he is without money), which resultantly affects other significant aspect of the individual’s life and functioning.

Although they do not depend on substances, behavioural addictions such as Wealth Acquisition Addiction (WAA) can be extremely dangerous and harmful, as people who suffer from this experience considerable deterioration in other significant areas of their lives. The reactions to WAA is similar to drugs or substance addictions, in their characteristics and consequences. From the Nigerian perspective, this study established a link between the Machiavellian philosophy of wealth acquisition, which justifies the acquisition and

retention of power at all cost, as a direct reflection of some Nigerians’ philosophy of wealth acquisition. The uneven distribution of wealth, coupled with the desire to rise above the poverty line, was also implicated as a causative factor of this obsession with wealth acquisition.

The paper also explored factors that may contribute to Wealth Acquisition Addiction, such as addictive personality, substance abuse and genetics. Suppression of empathy and compassion, lack of emotional intelligence, depression, moral entitlement and life dissatisfaction, has been identified as the psychosocial implications of WAA. Signs of Wealth Acquisition Addiction, such as denial, money secrecy and shame, money obsession, lack of money control and the inability to change maladaptive money behaviour, despite negative consequences were highlighted. The study also proffered psychological approaches to the treatment of WAA, such as Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) and Motivational Interviewing.

There is therefore a need for further studies on the epidemiology of Wealth Acquisition Addiction, since it is an evolving area of interest; especially with Nigerian samples, so as to further understand this construct, given the peculiarity of our economic and political climate.

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